

Deliverable D2.1

Cloud infrastructure (accessible from the AI4Life website)

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CI	Continuous Integration
D	Deliverable
de.NBI	German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure
DL	Deep Learning
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
v	Version

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Description of work	5
2.1 BioEngine Framework	6
2.2 Integration with Nvidia Triton Inference Server	6
2.3 Scalability and Continuous Integration	7
2.4 User Accessibility and Collaboration	7
3. Conclusion	7

Executive Summary

AI4Life is dedicated to democratizing access to modern Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods in biological imaging, building bridges between life science and computer vision researchers to expand the reach of cutting-edge techniques. A key part of this mission is to create cloud services to support the BioImage Model Zoo, making AI models easily accessible and runnable for both experts and non-experts.

In line with this mission, the focus of **Deliverable (D) 2.1** is the development and deployment of BioEngine, a cloud-based framework designed to facilitate the seamless execution of AI models directly from the BioImage Model Zoo website (<https://bioimage.io>). BioEngine incorporates Hypha, a central hub that manages a plethora of services including user management, object storage, and serverless app deployment. Integrated with Nvidia's Triton Inference Server, BioEngine enables dynamic Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) resource allocation to serve a wide array of models to a large user base, thereby eliminating the barriers of complex software and hardware requirements.

Over the past year, this cloud infrastructure has been rigorously tested and fine-tuned for robustness, scalability, and user-friendliness. Developed in close collaboration with Nvidia and various AI4Life partners, and deployable on multiple cloud environments such as de.NBI (German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure) and Google Cloud Platform, BioEngine stands as a pivotal component in achieving AI4Life's overarching goal of making AI accessible and efficient for the life sciences community.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, commenced in September 2022 and will continue until September 2025. The primary goal of AI4Life is to make advanced AI-based image analysis methods universally accessible, particularly to life scientists who may not have specialized training in programming or AI. This ambition is especially significant given that AI has radically transformed the landscape of microscopy image restoration, segmentation, and analysis. However, the technological demands of AI tools often pose a barrier to their widespread adoption.

Deliverable D2.1, the subject of this report, is squarely focused on **Task 2.2**, which aims to eliminate the complexities associated with setting up AI model execution environments. By providing zero-setup test run services through the BioImage Model Zoo website, we make it effortless for users to apply a plethora of models to their data and gain rapid biological insights. The cloud infrastructure, named BioEngine, serves as the backbone of this service. It includes a central hub called Hypha, which manages an array of functionalities from user management to object storage. Integrated with Nvidia's Triton Inference Server (<https://github.com/triton-inference-server/server>), BioEngine is capable of efficiently serving a multitude of models to users, dynamically allocating GPU resources to meet demand.

The development and deployment of BioEngine represent a multi-disciplinary effort, combining expertise in AI, cloud computing, and life sciences. Developed in collaboration with Nvidia and tested in various cloud environments, including de.NBI (part of the European Open Science Cloud, EOSC) and Google Cloud Platform, the BioEngine exemplifies AI4Life's commitment to fostering an ecosystem where AI models can be easily accessed, tested, and applied. This cloud infrastructure not only simplifies the user experience but also catalyzes a broader shift towards making AI models easily consumable, thereby aligning with AI4Life's long-term vision of democratizing AI in the life sciences and making AI and services more FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

2. Description of work

The central objective of the AI4Life project is to build a robust and unified repository for AI models in microscopy image analysis, addressing the needs of both expert and non-expert users. **Deliverable D2.1** under **Task 2.2** is particularly designed to make AI models more accessible and efficient for a broad user base, mainly focusing on those without specialized training in programming or AI.

2.1 BioEngine Framework

The cornerstone of **Task 2.2** is the BioEngine framework, a cloud-based computing architecture that serves as the fulcrum for all AI model-related activities. BioEngine consists of multiple integrated components, with Hypha acting as the central hub for communication and service management. Developed to be highly extensible, Hypha supports a wide range of functionalities, such as user management, virtual workspace management, object storage management, and serverless app deployment. A pivotal feature of Hypha is its remote procedure call protocol (*imjoy-rpc-v2*), which facilitates seamless, bidirectional communication among the various components and users connected to the system. This simplifies the task for developers in extending the system's features and capabilities.

The BioEngine server framework is mainly enabled by the following components:

- **hypha** for Remote Procedure Call (RPC) communication, user management, data storage, application & model serving. Source code: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/hypha>; The package is also available as a Python package in the pypi repository: <https://pypi.org/project/hypha/>.
- **hypha-k8s** for scalable deployment to Kubernetes clusters. Source code: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/hypha-k8s>
- **imjoy-rpc-v2** for enabling RPC communication and providing client support for Python and Javascript. Source code: <https://github.com/imjoy-team/imjoy-rpc/blob/master/imjoy-rpc-v2.md>

2.2 Integration with Nvidia Triton Inference Server

BioEngine integrates Nvidia's Triton Inference Server to enable efficient and dynamic model serving. This integration allows BioEngine to serve hundreds of different AI models from the BioImage Model Zoo to a large number of users simultaneously. Users can send custom images either from the BioImage Model Zoo website or from their desktop image analysis software such as ImageJ (<https://imagej.net>), napari (<https://napari.org>) or Icy (<https://icy.bioimageanalysis.org/>). Hypha forwards these requests to the Triton Inference Server, which then processes the data and returns the analytical results to the users.

The implementation of the Triton server integration is done through the `bioengine-model-runner` component, the source code is available at: <https://github.com/bioimage-io/bioengine-model-runner>.

2.3 Scalability and Continuous Integration

To ensure scalability and high performance, BioEngine has been tested on multiple cloud platforms, including the de.NBI cloud in the EU and the Google Cloud Platform in the US. Our ongoing collaboration with Nvidia's Triton Management Team has proven invaluable in optimizing the system for maximum efficiency and effectiveness. In terms of software development, we have implemented Continuous Integration (CI) services using Github Actions (<https://github.com/bioimage-io/bioengine-model-runner/actions>). Whenever a new model is uploaded, our CI system validates and converts it into a suitable format, making it immediately available for user testing through BioEngine.

2.4 User Accessibility and Collaboration

BioEngine is not just an Application Programming Interface (API) service; it also provides web applications attached to each model card in the BioImage Model Zoo (<https://bioimage.io/>), enabling non-experts to easily run models on their own data. We offer Jupyter Notebooks as additional resources to demonstrate programmatic access to BioEngine. Collaborating closely with AI4Life partners, we have enabled existing partner software like Napari and Icy to integrate seamlessly with our cloud infrastructure.

Through the development and deployment of BioEngine, the AI4Life project has taken a substantial step toward democratizing the use of AI in life sciences. This cloud-based framework acts as a one-stop solution for AI model deployment, testing, and execution, thereby fulfilling the objectives of **Task 2.2** and setting a new standard in the field of bioimage analysis.

3. Conclusion

AI4Life remains committed to its mission of democratizing access to cutting-edge AI methods in biological imaging, bridging the gap between life science researchers and computer vision specialists. **Deliverable D2.1**, encapsulated by the BioEngine cloud infrastructure, marks a significant milestone in this journey. BioEngine offers a scalable, robust, and user-friendly platform that removes the technological barriers often associated with AI tools, thereby making it feasible for a broader user base to employ advanced AI models in their research.

The BioEngine framework, developed in collaboration with Nvidia and multiple AI4Life partners, represents a multi-faceted approach to meet the needs of both expert and non-expert users. By integrating a plethora of functionalities — from user and object storage management to dynamic GPU resource allocation — BioEngine stands as a

comprehensive solution for AI model deployment and execution. Furthermore, its compatibility with multiple cloud environments and its integration with existing partner software like Napari and Icy make it a versatile tool for the life science community.

In summary, the work detailed in this report exemplifies AI4Life's vision of a future where AI models are easily accessible, reusable, and efficient. Due to limited computational power that we can afford through the project, the framework is mainly used for test runs of models for the BioImage Model Zoo. However, we will provide a more complete deployment toolkit in **Deliverable D2.2** (month 20) to enable user deployment of the BioEngine, thus allowing full scale analysis on their own computing infrastructure. Through the development and successful deployment of BioEngine, we are not just creating a tool but laying the groundwork for a transformative shift in how the life science community engages with AI. This sets the stage for a new paradigm in scientific exploration, fostering greater collaboration, and driving forward innovation in bioimage analysis.

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